

Table 2. Life history of *P. maidis* on maize in a greenhouse. IRRI, 1993.

	$\bar{x} \pm sd$
Egg incubation period (d)	5.2 \pm 0.8
Nymphal stadium (d)	
I	3.8 \pm 0.8
II	3.6 \pm 1.0
III	3.3 \pm 1.0
IV	3.2 \pm 0.6
V	3.3 \pm 0.5
Total immature developmental period (d)	22.4 \pm 4.8
Adult longevity (d)	
Male	10.1 \pm 3.3
Female	11.0 \pm 4.8

the four hosts ranged from 17.2 to 17.6 d. Fecundities of the females reared on each host were very similar to those initially tested as ovipositional hosts from adults reared in the stock culture on maize.

The incubation period of the egg stage on maize was 5.2 d (Table 2). Each of the five nymphal stadia lasted 3.2 to 3.8 d for a total developmental period of the egg and nymph of 22.4 d. The adult female lived 11.0 d while the male lived 10.1 d.

Rice is neither an ovipositional nor a developmental host of *P. maidis*, which develops best on maize, *R. cochinchinensis*, *P. maximum*, and *L. chinensis*. ■

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Biology of the maize orange leafhopper *Cicadulina bipunctata* (Melichar) on rice and maize

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The leafhopper *Cicadulina bipunctata* is a vector of rice leaf gall in the Philippines. Plant injury is by removal of leaf tissue and leaf galls. Excessive feeding causes leaf yellowing or wilting. Its biology was compared on rice and maize in a greenhouse with an average ambient temperature of 27.6 \pm 1.2 °C and relative humidity of 69.4 \pm 4.3%.

Newly emerged adult pairs were obtained from a stock culture and released to oviposit on rice and maize. The mean incubation period was determined from eggs extracted from plants and held on moist filter paper in petri dishes with 1% M-tegosept, a fungistatic agent. Ten neonate nymphs were individually reared on a one-tillered host plant covered with a 6- \times 25-cm cylindrical mylar cage with side and top nylon mesh (5 mm) vents. The duration of each instar was recorded from daily observations.

Life history of *C. bipunctata*^a on rice and maize in a greenhouse. IRRI, 1993.

	Rice			Maize			Difference ^b
	\bar{x}	\pm	sd	\bar{x}	\pm	sd	t-test
Egg incubation period (d)	7.5	\pm	0.8	7.5	\pm	0.5	ns
Nymphal stadium (d)							
I	3.0	\pm	0.0	2.5	\pm	0.5	
II	3.3	\pm	0.8	2.3	\pm	0.6	
III	3.5	\pm	0.5	2.0	\pm	0.0	
IV	3.4	\pm	1.0	2.1	\pm	0.3	
V	3.3	\pm	0.9	2.2	\pm	0.4	
Nymph developmental period (d)	16.5	\pm	3.2	11.1	\pm	1.8	**
Adult longevity							
Male	11.0	\pm	1.6	11.4	\pm	0.8	ns
Female	14.5	\pm	0.9	13.9	\pm	1.1	ns
Eggs laid (no./female)	15.3	\pm	4.5	729.0	\pm	34.4	**

^an = 10. ^bns = not significant (P > 0.05). ** = highly significant (P < 0.01).

Incubation period of whitish elongated eggs, normally laid singly on rice and maize, averaged 7.5 d on both (see table).

Neonate nymphs disperse in search of food, becoming increasingly mobile with age. The nymphs passed five nymphal instars in 16.5 d on rice, but the period was significantly shorter on maize (11.1 d). On rice, nymphal moltings occurred in 3.0, 3.3, 3.5, 3.4, and 3.3 d, while on maize, five nymphal stadia were observed in 2.5, 2.3, 2.0, 2.1, and 2.2 d

from first to fifth instar. Shorter nymph development indicates greater fitness on a plant host. Adult longevity was equal on rice and maize. On both the host plants, however, females lived longer (14 d) than the males (11 d). Fecundity averaged 15.3 eggs on rice and 729 eggs on maize.

We conclude that in the laboratory, *C. bipunctata* is more adapted to maize than to rice because of its shorter nymphal period and greater fecundity, but rice can sustain its development. ■